

Ethical Climate among SME Employees Has No Effect on Job Satisfaction in the Western Sugar Belt Kenya

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Abstract

The practice of business ethics has grown considerably over the last decade. Small business enterprises today are expected to meet standards of responsible business conduct. Moral decay has, however, reached high levels not only in the public sector but also in the business community including cane haulage transport MSEs. An estimated 120 ethical business violations attributed to transport firms have been reported repeatedly in the recent years in the Sugar Belt. Furthermore, 63% of contracted cane transport tractors were reported to have been involved in cane losses, with the situation worsening to 73% in the past years. Consequently, there have been calls for research on the possible effect of ethical business practices among SME employees and their job satisfaction. The objective of the study, therefore, was to examine the effect of ethical treatment towards employees on employee job satisfaction. The study was guided by the stakeholder theory and a conceptual model of the same theory aimed at assessing business/stakeholder relationships. A correlational survey design was adopted for the study. The study population was made up of 1,000 Cane Haulage MSE employees. A sample size of 100 based on a 90% response rate was used. Employees were selected using simple random techniques. Questionnaires were used to obtain data from the employees. Frequencies were used to show the distribution of responses. Correlations and regression analysis were used to assess associations between ethical treatment towards employees and job satisfaction. Pearson correlations revealed that good work safety facilities positively correlated with employee loyalty. Similarly, the correlations showed that job security negatively correlated with employee loyalty. Logistic regression results showed that job security negatively affected employee loyalty. Pearson correlations further revealed that job security positively correlated with the handling of employees. On the other hand, logistic regression indicated that there was no relationship between job security and the handling of employees. The study recommended that cane transport companies should increase job security for employees. The study also recommended that transport MSE managers should use these findings to improve cane transport services and save their businesses from imminent collapse

Keywords: Ethical climate, Job satisfaction

Background of the study

Scholars have defined ethical climate as the shared perception of ethically correct behavior and the way the organization should address ethical situations (Unal, 2012; Wang & Hsieh, 2012). Ethical climate in the workplace develops when employees believe there are certain standards and norms that the organization expects for behaviours and for resolving situations that develop in the workplace (Floyd et al., 2011). The organizational climate is the way that the organization defines routine practices supported by the reward system.

The perception of the employee concerning the organizational climate and the ethical climate subset develops based on their observation and experiences of the way the organization rewards different types of practices (Schneider, Ehrhart, & Macey, 2011). If the organization rewards actions that conform to an employee's ethical values and norms, the employee is likely to perceive the organization as having an ethical climate. Consequently, the ethical climate is a subjective construct consisting of the aggregate perceptions of the employees. The ethical climate of the organization is presumed to influence job satisfaction by reducing ambiguities in job roles when there is congruence between the ethics of the individual and the ethics of the organization (Unal, 2012).

In contrast to the perspective of Floyd, et al., (2011) that ethical climate is a component of employee behavior, some scholars suggest that ethical climate is a component of organizational culture (Schneider, et al., 2011; Tanner, et al., 2015). On the other hand, Job satisfaction refers to a sense of fulfillment, gratification, or contentment that develops as a result of working in a specific job (Collie, et al., 2012). Job satisfaction is perceived as an emotional response to all of the factors that the individual experiences in the place of employment (Federici, & Skaalvik, 2012). Job satisfaction can range from extreme dissatisfaction to extreme satisfaction and involves the objective and subjective understanding of the employee about the job (Eleswed & Mohammed, 2013).

The concept of job satisfaction is comprised of numerous variables such as perceptions of promotional opportunities, adequacy of compensation and benefits and relations with coworkers and supervisors (David, Gidwani, Birthare, & Singh, 2015; Sentuna, 2015; Singh & Jain, 2013). Job satisfaction variables are often categorized as intrinsic and extrinsic factors (Caricati, et al., 2014). Intrinsic factors involve higher-order variables such as the desire for recognition and advancement. Extrinsic factors are elements of the external environment, such as compensation, the comfort of the work environment, or perceptions of the quality of leadership.

The Job Characteristics Theory (Hackman & Oldham, 1980) emphasized that employees will be satisfied with their job if it includes a variety of work, independent thinking, and fosters feelings of responsibility.

In a review of previous research concerning ethical climate in organizations, Tanner, et al. (2015) reported that there is substantial evidence to conclude that a relationship exists between ethical climate and job satisfaction. The authors also proposed that the mechanism by which ethical climate influences job satisfaction is through a reduction in stress when there is congruence between an employee's personal ethics and the ethical orientation communicated by the organization. Other research has determined that employees who perceive the organization as ethical will also believe that the organization is fair towards them and will have higher job

Research by Floyd, et al. (2011) identified a relationship between different ethical orientations in organizations and job satisfaction. A negative correlation existed between an egoistic ethical climate and job satisfaction with the egoistic climate characterized by efforts to maximize personal gain. In contrast, a positive correlation existed between a benevolent ethical climate defined as a caring climate and job satisfaction. In addition, a positive correlation was found between a principled climate and job satisfaction with the organization adhering to a set of explicit principles. Khasawneh (2014) confirmed these findings and identified both positive and negative correlations between the types of ethical climate and job satisfaction.

The degree of importance of the various orientations of ethical climate for job satisfaction can vary (Bothrani, Jalali, Abbaszadah, Haghdoost, & Amiresmaili, 2012).

Wong and Li (2015) tested the theory that unethical behaviour by senior managers establishes the ethical climate of the organization and has a negative effect on job satisfaction. Their findings indicate that the unethical treatment of employees had the greatest negative effect on job satisfaction and was the most significant factor in establishing the ethical climate of the organization.

In the western Kenya region, cane transport SME Managers are reported to be engaged in ethical violations against their transport employees. On the other hand, these employees exhibit the behaviour of dissatisfaction. It became imperative therefore to carry out a study in order to ascertain a possible relationship between ethical climate and employee job satisfaction.

METHODOLOGY

The study population

Kombo & Delmo (2006), referred to a study population as a group of individuals from which samples were taken for measurement. Uma (2003) refers to the population as the entire group of people of interest that the researcher wishes to investigate.

In this regard, the study population for this study comprised of the key stakeholders in the sugar industry who were likely to be affected by cane haulage services. These included 1000 employees of cane haulage MSEs in Mumias Sugar Belt.

Determination and allocation of sample sizes

A sample size decision model developed by Krejcie and Morgan (1970) was used to determine the sample size of 100 key respondents from a population of 1000 employees.

90 employees filled and returned the questionnaires. This translates to a 90% response rate way above the 72% response recommended by John and Niel (1998).

Model specification

The single model utilized in the study is shown in figure 1, where the variables X (ethical treatment to employees) and M (employee satisfaction) depict direct effects between X and M. These steps *a* of Kenny and Barron (1986) model.

Figure 1: Kenny and Barron (1986)

a = the relation of X to M. The model equation recommended for the study is as follows:

$$Y = i_2 + c'X + bm + e_2$$

Step 2 of the Kenny and Barron four-step model shows that the initial variable is correlated with the mediator. M is used as the criterion variable in a regression equation and X, a predictor (it estimates and tests path *a*). This step essentially involves treating the mediator as if it were an outcome variable.

Table: 1 Frequencies of Responses on Ethical Treatment Towards Employees

Statement		SD	D	N	A	SA	TOTAL
Employees on good pension scheme	F	61	26	0	12	1	100
	%	61.0	26.0	0.0	12.0	1.0	100
Employees with full support to join Trade Union	F	30	48	5	13	4	100
	%	30.0	48.0	5.0	13.0	4.0	100
Employees promoted since they joined current Employer	F	43	36	0	11	10	100
	%	43.0	36.0	0.0	11.0	10.0	100
Employees with good work Safety Facilities	F	13	66	0	8	13	100
	%	13.0	66.0	0.0	8.0	13.0	100
Employees with competitive Salary	F	66	27	0	6	1	100

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Package	%	66.0	27.0	0.0	6.0	1.0	100
Employees with good job Security	F	42	25	2	25	6	100
	%	42.0	25.0	2.0	25.0	6.0	100
Employers give local Community Preference during employment	F	48	39	0	12	1	100
	%	48.0	39.0	0.0	12.0	1.0	100
Employees Gender balance during recruitment	F	56	39	1	4	0	100
	%	56.0	39.0	1.0	4.0	0.0	100
Employers solve financial problems beyond Employees salary	F	56	29	0	10	5	100
	%	56.0	29.0	0.0	10.0	5.0	100
Employers sponsor employees for further training	F	68	32	0	0	0	100
	%	68.0	32.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100

Source: Survey Data

When asked about their level of agreement on pension scheme enrolment, 61% (61) respondents strongly disagreed, 26% (26) disagreed, none was neutral, 12% (12) agreed while only 1% (1) strongly agreed to be a contributor in a pension scheme. On the question of being supported to join trade unions by the employer, 30% (30) strongly disagreed, 48% (48) disagreed, 5% (5) were neutral, 13% (13) were in agreement while only 4% (4) strongly agreed. When asked if they had been promoted, 43% (43) strongly disagreed, 36% (36) disagreed, none was neutral, 8% (8) agreed and 13% (13) strongly agreed to have been promoted. when asked about their work safety, 13% (13) strongly disagreed, 66% (66) disagreed, none was neutral, 8% (8) agreed and 13% (13) strongly agreed to have work safety facilities. On the question of having a competitive salary package, 66% (66) strongly disagreed, 27% (27) agreed, none was neutral, 6% (6) agreed, while only 1% (1) strongly agreed to have a good salary package. When asked about job related security, 42% (42) strongly disagreed, 25% (25) disagreed, 2% (2) were neutral, 25% (25) agreed while only 6% (6) strongly agreed to have job security. When asked if employers give local community preference during employment, 48% (48) strongly disagreed, 39% (39) disagreed, 1% (1) was neutral, 4% (4) agreed while none strongly agreed. On the question of gender balance during employment, 56% (56) strongly disagreed that there was a gender balance, 39% (39) disagreed, 1% (1) was neutral, 4% (4) agreed and none strongly agreed. When respondents were asked if their employers solve their financial problems, 56% (56) strongly disagreed, 29% (29) disagreed, none was neutral, 10% (10)

agreed that their employers solve their financial problems while only 5% (5) strongly agreed. When they were asked if their employers sponsor them for further studies, 68% (68) strongly disagreed, 32% (32) disagreed, none was neutral, none agreed and none strongly agreed.

It can be observed from table 1 that the majority of the employees of the cane transport companies seemed to disagree with all the statements regarding ethical treatment towards employees by the employer. This can be interpreted to mean that in the opinion of employees, cane transport employers did not treat them well.

Employee job satisfaction indicators

Statement		SD	D	N	A	SA	TOTAL
Friendliness of co-workers	F	3	1	3	46	47	100
	%	3.0	1.0	3.0	46.0	47.0	100
Way in which the company takes care of employees complains	F	15	44	23	17	1	100
	%	15.0	44.0	23.0	17.0	1.0	100
Salary and amount of work done	F	34	59	5	2	0	100
	%	34.0	59.0	5.0	2.0	0.0	100
Praise for job well done	F	5	24	24	46	1	100
	%	5.0	24.0	24.0	46.0	1.0	100
Working conditions	F	24	48	15	13	0	100
	%	24.0	48.0	15.0	13.0	0.0	100
Way in which employer handles employees	F	7	36	36	21	0	100
	%	7.0	36.0	36.0	21.0	0.0	100
Recognition for the work done	F	11	49	14	26	0	100
	%	11.0	49.0	14.0	26.0	0.0	100
Chances of advancement	F	36	36	21	7	0	100
	%	36.0	36.0	21.0	7.0	0.0	100

Table 2: Response frequencies of employee's job satisfaction

Source: Survey Data

Several indicators on employee's job satisfaction were used to assess whether the content of job satisfaction had a mediating role between ethical treatment towards employees and employees' perceived enterprise performance. These indicators consisted of co-workers, the way in which the company takes care of employees' complains, salary and amount of work done, praise for a job well done, working conditions, the way in which employer handles employees, recognition for work done, and chances of advancement. All responses were derived from a five-point Likert scale which entailed "Strongly Disagree" (SD), "Disagree" (D), "Neutral" (N), "Agree" (A), and "Strongly Agree" (SA) having corresponding values of 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, respectively. The results were recorded in table 4.16.

When respondents were asked to rate their satisfaction with the friendliness of co-workers, 3% (3) were strongly dissatisfied, 1% (1) was dissatisfied, 3% (3) were neutral, 46% (46) agreed and 47% (47) strongly agreed to satisfaction with fellow worker's friendliness. On the question of satisfaction with the way the company takes care of its employees, 15% (15) strongly disagreed, 44% (44) disagreed, 23% (23) were neutral, 17% (17) agreed and only 1% (1) strongly agreed. When asked if they were satisfied with the salary and amount of work done, 34% (34) strongly disagreed, 59% (59) disagreed, 5% (5) were neutral, 2% (2) agreed and none strongly agreed. When they were asked if they receive praise for work done, 5% (5) strongly disagreed, 24% (24) disagreed, 24% (24) were neutral, 46% (46) agreed and only 1% (1) strongly agreed. When they were asked if they were satisfied with working conditions, 24% (24) strongly disagreed, 48% (48) disagreed, 15% (15) were neutral, 13% (13) agreed and none strongly agreed. When respondents were asked if they were satisfied with the way the employer handles employees, 7% (7) expressed strong dissatisfaction, 36% (36) disagreed, 36% (36) were neutral, 21% (21) agreed and none strongly agreed. On the question of recognition for good work done, 11% (11) expressed strong disagreement, 49% (49) disagreed, 14% (14) were neutral, 26% (26) agreed and none strongly agreed. When asked about their satisfaction with chances of advancement, 36% (36) strongly disagreed, 36% (36) disagreed, 21% (21) were neutral, 7% (7) agreed that they had chances of advancement and none strongly agreed.

It was observed among indicators of employees' job satisfaction in Table 1 that most employees had a positive opinion about the friendliness of co-workers and receiving praise for a job well done. On the other hand, the majority were negative about the way the company takes care of employees' complains, salary and amount of work done, working conditions, way in which employer handles employees, recognition for the work done, and chances of advancement. This could explain the fact that employees hardly have issues with each other. The bone of contention is usually with their employer. It explains why employees were satisfied with fellow employees and dissatisfied with their employer. The satisfaction level of employees sharply varies with the findings of Tetra link (2009), who obtained a high satisfaction index for employees of Kenya Sugar Board. The variance could be explained by the fact that Tetra links (2009) investigated job satisfaction levels of employees of different stakeholders in the sugar industry.

Pearson correlations between employee ethical factors and job satisfaction factors.

Table 3 presents the results from cross-tabulation to assess the correlation between employee ethical factors and job satisfaction factors assessed by employees. Ethical climate variables were used with job satisfaction indicators identified in Table 3 below. The Table displays Pearson correlations between employee ethical factors and job satisfaction factors.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation of ethical treatment to employees factors and job satisfaction factors (p-value)

Employee Ethical Factor	Job Satisfaction Factor						
	EJS2	EJS3	EJS4	EJS5	EJS6	EJS7	EJS8
ETE4	7.109 (0.927)	7.302 (0.544)	12.922 (0.353)	13.732 (0.079)	5.866 (0.746)	6.520 (0.678)	9.428 (0.335)
ETE6	18.040 (0.340)	9.780 (0.747)	15.746 (0.597)	10.014 (0.574)	18.571 (0.046)**	12.262 (0.348)	7.343 (0.870)

** P-value < 0.05

Key

ETE6 employer cannot sack easily

EJS6 the way boss handles employees

Source: Survey Data

Table 3 suggested that there was a significant positive association between Employees with good job security; ETE6 and way employer handles employees, EJS6; $r = 18.571(p < 0.05)$. This implies that when an employee's job security increased, employees became more satisfied with the way they were handled. This is a linear relationship. The true nature of the relationship was explored in the foregoing logistic regression models, which were fitted to ascertain whether indeed there was a significant relationship between the dependent variable, ETE 6, employees with good job security and mediating variable EJS 6, satisfaction with the way the employer handles employees. The results were displayed in Table 4.18 to show the logistic regression output for step 2 of Kenny and Baron (1986)

Table 4 displays path **a** of the four mediation steps of Kenny and Barron (1986)

Table 4: Path a of Baron & Kenny steps

Step	Regression and Predictor	Outcome	Unstandardized	Standardized	95% CI		P value	Effect size	Power analysis	
	path(s) tested		coefficient B	coefficient Beta	LL	LU				
2	a	ETE6	EJS6	-0.117	-0.133	-0.292	0.058	0.186**	d=-0.288	0.86

Source; Researcher P-value <0.05**

Key

ETE6 employer cannot sack easily

EJS6 the way boss handles employees

Source: Survey Data

According to table 4.18 and figure 4.2 step 2 of Baron and Kenny (1986) did not pass $B = -0.117$, ($p > 0.05$). Consequently, H_{20} was accepted and the alternative rejected. This suggests that there was no evidence that employees with good job security influenced satisfaction with the way employers handle their employees.

This finding is inconsistent with a number of studies on organizational situations cited by Kol and Boo (2001); ethical practices were reported to lead to positive job attributes and outcomes. In other words, employees who perceive their organizations to be ethical are also likely to perceive their organizations as being fair to them; this intern is likely to enhance job satisfaction, hence organizational ethics and job satisfaction expected to be positively linked.

These study findings are equally inconsistent with findings by Sims and Kroeck (1994), Viswesvaran and Deshpande (1996), who found that lack of an ethical fit between employees and their organization can result in job dissatisfaction. Similarly, our findings disagree with the position taken by Bellizi and Hite (1989), which

opines that job satisfaction of salespeople was weakened if they perceive the organizations are rewarding the unethical behaviour of co-workers.

This scenario can be explained by the fact that when employees perceive strong top management support for ethical behaviour, a favourable ethical climate and a strong association between ethical behaviour and career success in the organization than they are also likely to have a higher level of job satisfaction. The findings of this study contradict a study by Honey Cult et al. (1995), which concluded that ethical perceptions of the industry negatively influenced job satisfaction levels. This would be an indication that if ethical standards at the leadership are low and the employees perceive the overall industry to have higher ethical standards, the employee would understandably become disenchanted with the job.

On the contrary, our study is in agreement with findings of a similar study by Sims and Kroeck (1994), who studies the influence of ethical fit on employees' attitudes and intentions to turnover. Their findings revealed that job satisfaction was not significantly related to the fit between the current work ethical climate and the employees expressed preferences. This consistency could be due to the fact that both studies adopted the Minnesota satisfaction questionnaire. On the other hand, this could be due to the fact that satisfaction is a measure of job attitudes, while ethical climate work climate is a measure of the organization.

Results for this study are equally in agreement with a study conducted by Vittel and Davis (1990a), which empirically examined the relationship between ethics and job satisfaction for 61 management information system professionals. Their results indicated that most professionals were more satisfied with the various measured dimensions of their job when top management stressed ethical behaviour. They were all found to be related to job satisfaction. This consistency could be accounted for by similarities in the measures of the variables.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommended that employers of sugarcane transport companies should consider treating their employees with decorum by improving working conditions because good working conditions serve as an incentive, which improves employee satisfaction with their job. If the employer would be keen to do this, the study concludes that an improved level of employee satisfaction would automatically guarantee improved social performance to transporters.

References

- i. Borhani, F., Jalali, T., Abbaszadeh, A., Haghdoost, A., & Amiresmaili, M. (2012). Nurses' perception of ethical climate and job satisfaction. *Journal of Medical Ethics and History of Medicine*, 5, 6.
- ii. Caricati, L., La Sala, R., Marletta, G., Pelosi, G., Ampollini, M., Fabbri, A., Ricchi, A., Scardino, M., Artioli, G., & Mancini, T. (2014). Work climate, work values, and professional commitment as predictors of job satisfaction among nurses. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 22(8), 984-994.
- iii. Collie, R., Shapka, J., & Perry, N. (2012). School climate and social-emotional learning: Predicting teacher stress, job satisfaction, and teacher efficacy. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 104(4), 1189-1204.
- iv. David, S., Gidwani, R., Birthare, N., & Singh, P. (2015). Impacts of job satisfaction and organizational commitment: A study describing influence of gender difference on job satisfaction and organizational commitment. *International Journal of Core Engineering and Management*, 2(1), 93-111.
- v. Eleswed, M. & Mohammed, F. (2013). The impact of gender, age, years of experience, educational level, and position type on job satisfaction and organizational commitment. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4(11), 108-119.

- vi. Federici, R., & Skaalvik, E. (2012). *Principal self-efficacy: Relations with burnout, job satisfaction and motivation to quit. Social Psychology and Education, 16*, 295-320.
- vii. Floyd, K., Yerby, J., & Santiago, J. (2011). *Information systems faculty perceptions of ethical work climate and job satisfaction. Proceedings of the Southern Association for Information Systems Conference (pp. 67-72). Atlanta GA: SAIS.*
- viii. Hackman, J.R., & Oldham, G.R. (1980). *Work redesign. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.*
- ix. Kenny, D.A. & Baron, R.M. (1986). *The moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic and statistical considerations. Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 51(1)*, 1173-1182.
- x. Kenny, D.A., Bolger and Korchmaros, J.D. (2003) *Lower Level Mediation in multilevel models. Psychological methods, 8*, 115-128.
- xi. Khasawneh, S. (2014). *The influence of ethical climate on job satisfaction of university human resources. International Journal of Management in Education, 8(3)*, 265-280.
- xii. Kombo, K.D., & Delmo, L.A.T. (2006). *Proposal and Thesis Writing: Africa, Pauline Publications, ISBN 0831493719.*
- xiii. Schneider, B., Ehrhart, M. G., & Macey, W. H. (2011). *Perspectives on organizational climate and culture. In S. Zedeck (Ed.), APA handbook of industrial and organizational psychology: Vol. 1. Building and developing the organization (pp. 373–414). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.*
- xiv. Sentuna, M. (2015). *Investigation of job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and self-esteem of physical education teachers according to gender. International Online Journal of Education Sciences, 7(2)*, 93-101.
- xv. Singh, N. & Jain, S. (2013). *Job attitude, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment among school teachers: A study on gender differences. Zenith International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 3(4)*, 248-257.
- xvi. Tanner, E., Tanner, J., & Wakefield, K. (2015). *Panacea or paradox? The moderating role of ethical climate. Journal of Personal Selling and Sales Management, 35(2)*, 175-190.
- xvii. Uma, S. (2003). *Fourth Edition Research Methods for Business: A Skill Building Approach. (Asia) John Wiley & sons Pte Ltd.*
- xviii. Unal, F. (2012). *Relationship between organizational commitment and ethical climate: The mediating role of job satisfaction. Journal of WEI Economics and Business, 1(1)*, 92-105.
- xix. Wang, Y., & Hsieh, H. (2012). *Toward a better understanding of the link between ethical climate and job satisfaction: A multilevel analysis. Journal of business Ethics, 105*, 535-545.
- xx. Wong, S., & Li, J. (2015). *Will hotel employees' perceptions of unethical managerial behavior affect their job satisfaction. International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management, 27(5)*, 853-877.